

PROBLEMS CAUSED BY EXCESSIVE GROUNDWATER CONSUMPTION AND THEIR PRACTICAL SOLUTIONS

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Abstract: In this article, a number of problems caused by the overuse of groundwater are studied together with their causes, observation areas and conditions. At the same time, a number of practical solutions to the existing problems have been proposed in a social, political and technical approach.

Key words : Groundwater, wells, drought, groundwater level, aquifer, subsidence, transboundary water sources, groundwater management .

Groundwater is the world's largest source of fresh water. When most people think of freshwater, they imagine rivers, wetlands, lakes, or reservoirs. But 30 times more fresh water than above is stored underground and out of sight. In fact, only 1% of the available fresh water can be seen on the surface of the earth, because two-thirds of the fresh water on the surface is in the eternal glaciers and snows of the mountains and almost one-third is groundwater. [1]In many parts of the world, especially where there is no surface water supply, domestic, agricultural and industrial water needs can be met only by using groundwater. About a third of the world's population uses groundwater for drinking water. [2]Groundwater is usually of higher quality than surface water and is suitable for human consumption, but sometimes contaminants are caused by natural factors (if the aquifer is very rich in dissolved salts or if certain rocks as a result of natural erosion) or human activities (for example, septic tank construction or agriculture) also reach underground aquifers. Due to the high quality and availability of groundwater, it is widely used worldwide. To put the numbers into perspective, 70 percent of global groundwater consumption is used for agriculture, while [3]38 percent of irrigated land relies entirely on groundwater sources. [4]

Figure 1 Global distribution of freshwater

According to the information of the State Geological Committee, as of January 2011, the consumption of underground water in Uzbekistan was 75.6 million m³ [5] per day 13.3 mln.m³ of this water is used to supply the country with drinking water (in 2010), 2.13 mln.m³ for production and technical water supply , 1.3 mln.m³ for irrigation of crops and pastures from underground water used. In most cases, these underground water resources meet hygienic requirements , and drinking water quality control is in accordance with the State Standards of Uzbekis

Groundwater consumption

Groundwater use is increasing day by day. For information, worldwide groundwater use was 312 km³ [6] in 1960, 743 km³ in 2000, and today this figure has increased to 982 km³ [7] . From this it can be understood that the consumption of underground water is growing. Although, as we noted above, groundwater is an important resource that supplies drinking water to billions of people and supports agriculture, industry, and environmental protection activities worldwide, its overuse is harmful to the environment. can lead to various serious problems that have a great impact on both human society. [8]

Research method

In this article, the long-term average consumption of groundwater is analyzed on a world scale and in the case of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and environmental, social and political problems arising due to the increasing consumption of groundwater are studied. At the same time, the factors affecting the sharp increase in the demand for underground water are studied, and several solutions to the existing problems are given.

Development of new methods of water use and improvement of existing ones based on the increase of underground water saccharin ; improvement of technological processes of groundwater management; environmentally safe technology and techniques, as well as the methodology of application based on the demand of consumers for regions in the section of specific types of consumers.

Analysis and results

One of the main problems caused by overuse of groundwater is depletion of aquifers. [9]As groundwater is consumed faster than it can be replenished, it can cause aquifers to dry up, leading to long-term water shortages. This affects not only the availability of water for drinking and irrigation, but also the sustainable functioning of ecosystems that rely on groundwater. This process is manifested in the form of drying up of wells, which are considered underground water sources, or a sharp decrease in the water level. [10]For information, the underground sub-level was 2.15 meters in 2014, and now it has decreased by 3.23 meters to 5.38 meters. [11]In some regions, this indicator is significantly higher, and in some regions of Navoi, Samarkand, Jizzakh, Kashkadarya, Namangan, Fergana and Andijan regions, its level has decreased to 5 meters . [12]

Another important problem associated with overexploitation of groundwater . As aquifers are depleted, the land above them can sink, damaging infrastructure and increasing the risk of flooding. In addition, loss of agricultural productivity can result from land subsidence, affecting food production and livelihoods. For information, 17,000 m² of the US territory was damaged by landslides, which cost the economy approximately 125 million dollars per year. damages in the amount of dollars . About 60% of these subsidences occurred as a result of extraction of underground fluids (groundwater, oil, gas). [13]

Land slides

In coastal areas, over-abstraction of groundwater can lead to saltwater intrusion, where saltwater from the ocean seeps into freshwater aquifers. This can contaminate drinking water supplies and degrade agricultural land, creating serious problems for communities that rely on groundwater for their water needs. Groundwater extraction is a major cause of saltwater intrusion. Under initial conditions, the saltwater interior is bounded by the higher pressure of the freshwater column due to its higher elevation. digging underground water withdrawal can lower freshwater levels, depress the freshwater column, and allow denser saltwater to move laterally inland.(13) At Cape May, New Jersey, since the 1940s, water withdrawals have lowered groundwater levels by up to 30 meters. has resulted in water levels falling below sea level and contamination of water supply wells. [14]

There are also political and economic problems related to the use of underground water, and today, with increasing water scarcity, this problem is becoming an urgent part of the agenda for the world community. For example, the Nubian underground water source is used by countries such as Egypt, Chad, Libya and Sudan. The scope of transboundary problems can be interregional, interstate or international. In all cases, the crux of the problem is that it is difficult to determine exactly which side is using too much water to contribute to the depletion of water resources. An excellent overview of transboundary aquifers, including hydrogeological, economic, legal, institutional and environmental issues, is provided by Puri, and a comprehensive atlas of international transboundary aquifers is developed by Puri and Aurelie. [15]

Addressing these challenges requires sustainable management practices. This includes monitoring and regulating groundwater use , promoting water conservation, and implementing policies to prevent overuse. International cooperation is also important in solving transboundary groundwater problems

and ensuring fair use of this important resource.

A multifaceted approach is needed to ensure sustainable management and long-term use of groundwater. Here are some suggestions as solutions to these problems:

One of the main solutions to over-consumption of groundwater is to implement sustainable water management practices. This includes setting limits on the amount of groundwater that can be extracted, as well as implementing regulations and monitoring systems to ensure compliance with these limits. By carefully managing and regulating the use of groundwater, we can help prevent over-extraction and sustainably use water resources.

Another important solution is to encourage water conservation efforts. This may include measures such as increasing the efficiency of irrigation in agriculture, promoting water-saving technologies in industry, and encouraging more efficient use of water in people's daily lives. By reducing overall water consumption, we can help ease pressure on groundwater resources and ensure their long-term use.

In addition, it is necessary to address the interdependence of surface and groundwater for effective management of these resources. This includes measures such as protecting and restoring natural habitats, implementing water-sensitive land-use planning strategies, and promoting sustainable practices that help maintain natural water flows and recharge aquifers.

Addressing overexploitation of groundwater also requires attention to pollution and climate change. These include reducing pollution from industrial and agricultural activities, implementing measures to clean up contaminated groundwater sources, and mitigating the effects of climate change on water availability and quality.

Also important to involve local communities in decision-making processes and consider the social, economic and environmental consequences of groundwater use. By working with local stakeholders and addressing their needs and concerns, we can ensure that solutions are effective and sustainable in the long term.

Conclusion

The research findings suggest that addressing groundwater overexploitation is complex and multifaceted, involving sustainable water management practices, water conservation efforts, pollution control, and climate change mitigation. requires an approach. By implementing these measures, we can work to ensure the long-term availability of groundwater for future generations while meeting the needs of people and the environment.

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